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THE DYNAMICS OF THE COMPONENTS IN THE TRIAD PROBLEM-SOLVING MODEL OF DESIGN

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ABSTRACT

The objectives of this study are to investigate the general patterns of the triadic components drawn from the triad problem-solving model of design and to examine how the triadic components are associated with design task, process, and outcome. We conducted the protocol analysis with trashcan design tasks at two different determinization levels and the post-experiment survey. Through the protocol analysis, we identified that both the percentage and increase rate of the solution category were highest while those of the problem category were lowest. This indicates that designers spend most times on creating solutions while least times on analyzing design problems, and these patterns of the triadic components become more dominant as the problem-solving activities progressed. Through correlation analysis, we found the positive effect of the goal-oriented problem-solving process on the concept generation and the importance of the analyzing problems to produce solutions with better functional utility.

Keywords: Triad Problem-Solving Model of Design, Triadic Components, Protocol Analysis, Design Evaluation

INTRODUCTION

There have been a large number of preceding studies that have interpreted design activity through two paradigms: rational problem-solving relating to positivism and reflection-in-action which is connected to constructionism (Dorst & Dijkhuis, 1995; Joseph, 1996; Dorst, 1997; Cross, 1999; Coyne, 2005). Rational problem-solving, as proposed by Simon (1996), is a design process that emphasizes

the analytic aspect of design activities. Reflection-in-action, as proposed by Schön (1983), is a design activity that indicates the restraints of technical rationality and illustrates the importance of the synthetic aspect of design activities. There have been various arguments or attempts to satisfy both paradigms by emphasizing the importance of balancing the two paradigms (Joseph, 1996; Dorst, 1997; Cross, 1999; María & Narváez, 2000; Coyne, 2005; Daughtry, et al., 2009). In order to establish a model for describing the simultaneity of the two paradigms, in Kwak and Kim's study (2006, 2008), the subject matter of design was newly defined as a quasi-determinate goal area, and the triad problem-solving model of design with a controllable determinization level was established based on the quasi-determinate goal area. The term of 'quasi-determinate' was defined as 'determinate as a determinized boundary but indeterminate within the boundary,' and 'determinize' was defined as 'to transform the indeterminate state into the quasi-determinate state.' The proposed model is a goal-oriented model that distinguishes a goal from a solution and transforms the binominal relationship between a problem and a solution into a triadic relationship among a problem, a solution, and a goal. The objectives of this study are first to validate the proposed model by examining the general patterns of the triadic components through empirical study and second to investigate how the triadic components are associated with design task, process, and outcome.

THE TRIAD PROBLEM-SOLVING MODEL OF DESIGN

The development of the triad problem-solving model of design with a controllable determinization level

has been described in our previous study (Kwak & Kim, 2006, 2008). We shall not reproduce the complete model, but rather provide a brief summary. The triad problem-solving model of design was a goal-oriented problem-solving model based on the triad relationship among a problem, a solution, and a goal (Fig. 1). The proposed model is composed of several parts: a problem area, a goal area, a solution area, a solution evaluation, determinization level and a goal evaluation. The explanations about each component are as follows:

- **Problem Area:** The ‘problem area’ is defined as a discovered situation, condition, or issue that is yet to be resolved. As the property of problem area in design research is quasi-determinate, the scientific approach of discovery can be partly applied in this area.
- **Goal Area:** The ‘goal area’ is defined as the purpose, aim, or objective toward which a designer’s endeavor is directed or that a plan is intended to achieve. It involves designers’ plans, intentions, and directions to achieve that purpose or aim. Designers define goals either to solve the discovered problem or to create better and more satisfying solutions without a certain problem. As the property of goal area in design research is quasi-determinate, the scientific approach of discovery can be partly applied in this area.
- **Solution Area:** The ‘solution area’ is defined as a

disposition of or response to a problem, difficulty or puzzle or alternatively as a response to a goal. In design, a solution is not the correct or definite answer to a problem, but a response or responsive result to a problem or a goal. The property of this area in design research is indeterminate, and therefore the non-scientific approach of invention can be applied.

- **Solution Evaluation:** The criteria for solution evaluation are not ‘right or wrong’ (the production of truth), but rather ‘good or bad’ (the degree of satisfaction) (Newell & Simon, 1972; Cross, 1982; Lawson, 1984; Cross, 1989; Bonsiepe, 1995; Simon, 1996; Owen, 2005). Good or bad is determined based on how successfully the goal is satisfied and how effectively the given problems are resolved. When the solution is good, the solution becomes the final solution (Jonas, 1993). However, if the solution is evaluated as bad, the problems of the solution should be found through evaluation, and an iterative problem-solving process (Swann, 2002) should be executed.
- **Determinization Level:** The determinization level of the goal area is defined as the degree in which a designer determinizes the boundary of the goal area. The more concretely does a designer define the determinized boundary of the goal area, the higher the determinization level is. The determinization level of the goal area is

Figure1. Triad problem-solving model of design

controllable, and it determines the proportion between discovery and invention in the triad problem-solving model of design.

- **Goal Evaluation:** Goal evaluation is an evaluation of the determinization level of the goal area. If the determinization level is evaluated as good, it is deemed to be at the proper level to aid in problem-solving activity toward a given problem. Conversely, if the determinization level is evaluated as bad, iterative processes that seek to find the proper determinization level are needed.

EMPIRICAL APPROACH

In order to analyze design activity based on the triad problem-solving model of design, research questions were defined as follows:

- (1) In the design process, how are the triadic components of the triad problem-solving model of design expressed through design activity?
- (2) How are the triadic components of the triad problem-solving model of design correlated with design task, process, and outcome?

The protocol analysis was conducted to examine the general patterns of the triadic components, and the post-experiment survey was administered to investigate how the triadic components were associated with design task, process, and outcome.

PARTICIPANTS

In order to examine the fact that the established model can be applied to general designers, three male and five female university students from the Seoul area participated in the study. All participants were majoring in industrial design at the same university. All participants were paid with \$US100.

DESIGN TASKS

Trashcan design problems at two different determinization levels were given to the participants as design tasks (Kwak, 2008).

Design Task 1 [Low Determinization Level]: Design a new trashcan which satisfies user's need by solving the problems of the current trashcans.

Design Task 2 [High Determinization Level]: Design a trashcan which satisfies the following conditions: (1) In order to treat garbage from food, the trashcan should be designed such that the garbage is relatively not visible and prevent the leakage of any

garbage stench; (2) When dumping garbage, the garbage should not stick to the trashcan; (3) Reducing unpleasantness to the most when touching trashcan.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

The experimental setup was constructed with reference to the 'Delft Protocols Workshop (Cross, Christiaans, & Dorst, 1996).' The experiments were conducted in a design room equipped with video and audio recording facilities, and supplied with table and chairs, drawing pad, pens and pencils, and a ruler. Neither the existing products nor materials to get information were provided in order to control these variables.

One experimenter guided the experiment as a moderator, and the other experimenter who was hidden by a partition controlled the video recording.

PROCEDURES

The experimental procedures were composed referring to the 'Delft Protocol Workshop.' After the short introduction about the experiment, a think aloud training exercise was conducted in order for the designer to become accustomed to thinking aloud. Then, the designer signed in the consent form, and the session began. All of the designers experienced two design tasks at different determinization levels. Each design task was performed for 60 minutes. After each designer's completion of all the design tasks, the interviews were executed to collect the retrospective verbal accounts, and the post-experiment survey was administered to each designer in order to assess the design problems, their process and solutions.

TRIAD CODING SCHEME

In order to analyze the patterns of the triadic components, we coded the data by a triad problem-solving model coding scheme (Triad coding scheme), which is composed of Problem (P), Goal (G), and Solution (S). The intercoder reliability was checked through the training procedures using the proportional reduction in loss (PRL) approach (Rust & Cooil, 1994).

The Table 1 describes the definition and the attributes of each category of Triad coding scheme with the corresponding examples. Most of the

examples are taken from the protocol data of the designer number 1's problem-solving process of design task 1.

EVALUATION MEASURES

In order to investigate the correlation among the triadic components and the design task, process, and outcome, the post-experiment survey was administered to each designer. On the post-experiment survey, participants evaluated the design problem, the problem-solving process of design, and the design solution on 15 different Likert-type items with a 5-point scale. The two evaluation items for the design problem were: difficult-easy, boring-interesting. The seven evaluation items for the problem-solving process of design were as follows: (1) How well were the design concepts generated in the problem-solving process? : badly generated-well generated, (2) How creative was the problem-solving process? : not creative-very creative, (3) In the problem-solving process, how much was the design solution developed in details? How concretely was the design solution developed?: abstractly-concretely, (4) Was the designer's problem-solving process free-flowing or determined/planned? : free-flowing-determined/planned, (5) How easy was the problem-solving process? : difficult-easy, (6) How interesting was the problem-solving process? : boring-interesting,

(7) How much did the designer redefine the design problem? : not at all-very much. The evaluation criteria for the design solutions were constructed based on several criteria presented in the previous studies (Baxter, 1995; Dorst, 1997; Jo, 1997; Owen, 2005; Kim et al., 2006). They were total judgment (better/worse), appropriateness, creativity, aesthetics, functional utility, and usability.

CODING PROCEDURE

As the results of the coding procedures, the intercoder reliability measures of all of the 16 samples for Triad categories exceeded the proper PRL level of .70 (Rust & Cooil, 1994). The PRL level for Triad categories ranged from 0.92 to 0.98 (M: 0.95).

RESULTS

The experimental results include the protocol analysis results on Triad categories, and the correlation between protocol analysis results and evaluation results.

PROTOCOL ANALYSIS RESULTS ON TRIAD CATEGORIES

Eight designers' problem-solving activities for two design tasks at different determinization levels were analyzed by the Triad categories in order to examine how the three components of the established triadic

	Definition	Attributes
Problem (P)	A discovered situation, condition, or issue that is yet resolved ex) The existing trashcan are not pretty (5)*	'closed' state: • the discovered problem • Something was discovered. • a completed state ex) I considered the uncleanness. (92)
	A negative evaluation of S ex) S: I thought of a trashcan with an automatic lid. (95) P: It is inappropriate for public trashcan because it lacks humane feeling. (96)	
Goal (G)	A negative evaluation of G ex) G: This will provide more convenience. (62) P: But it can generate more odor. (63)	'open' state: • searching a goal or a solution to satisfy a goal • Something should be searched or achieved. • a progressive state ex) Well... concerning the resolution of the uncleanness (45)
	Purpose, aim, or objective toward which a designer's endeavor is directed or which a plan is intended to achieve ex) Considering colors (15)	
Solution (S)	A positive evaluation of S ex) S: ... made the entrance with an inclination of these degrees. (28) G: Easy to throw trash (29)	'closed' state: • the created solution • Something was made or created. • a completed state ex) a trashcan for food (9)

* The numbers in the parentheses represent the number of segment unit by order of the designer number 1's protocol data.

Table1. The definitions and the attributes of each category of Triad coding scheme

model are expressed through design activity.

Table 2 shows the counts and the percentage of each Triad category. In all of the protocol data from 16 subjects, the solution category was displayed most, and the problem category was displayed least.

The analysis of variance (ANOVA) examining the effect of the Triad categories on the percentage, showed the Triad categories to have a significant effect ($F_{(2, 14)} = 104.744, p < 0.0005$). The percentage of S category ($M = 51.7\%$) was more than the percentage of G category ($M = 32.0\%$; $F_{(1, 15)} = 70.776, p < 0.0005$), and the percentages of both of these categories were more than the percentage of P category ($M = 16.3\%$; $F_{(1, 15)} = 339.921, p < 0.0005$ for S category, and $F_{(1, 15)} = 46.939, p < 0.0005$ for G category).

The F is the variance of the group means divided by the mean of the within-group variances (Analysis of Variance, 2011), and the p -value is defined as the smallest level of significance that would lead to rejection of the null hypothesis H_0 (Montgomery, 2001).

Designers	Task	P	G	S	Total Units
1	1	31 (19.9)	51 (32.7)	74 (47.4)	156 (100.0)
	2	44 (23.0)	53 (27.7)	94 (49.2)	191(100.0)
2	1	29 (19.0)	37 (24.2)	87 (56.9)	153 (100.0)
	2	26 (21.1)	40 (32.5)	57 (46.3)	123 (100.0)
3	1	27 (22.1)	27 (22.1)	68 (55.7)	122 (100.0)
	2	20 (13.2)	43 (28.5)	88 (58.3)	151 (100.0)
4	1	22 (23.4)	23 (24.5)	49 (52.1)	94 (100.0)
	2	17 (14.4)	37 (31.4)	64 (54.2)	118 (100.0)
5	1	41 (17.1)	94 (39.2)	105 (43.8)	240 (100.0)
	2	14 (8.9)	64 (40.8)	79 (50.3)	157 (100.0)
6	1	22 (15.0)	56 (38.1)	69 (46.9)	147 (100.0)
	2	9 (9.3)	29 (29.9)	59 (60.8)	97 (100.0)
7	1	37 (16.4)	77 (34.1)	112 (49.6)	226 (100.0)
	2	24 (13.8)	65 (37.4)	85 (48.9)	174 (100.0)
8	1	30 (12.0)	80 (32.1)	139 (55.8)	249 (100.0)
	2	22 (13.0)	62 (36.7)	85 (50.3)	169 (100.0)
Avg.		25.9 (16.3)	52.4 (32.0)	82.1 (51.7)	160.4 (100.0)

Table 2. The counts and the percentage of Triad categories [counts (percentage)]

The accumulative segments of each Triad category were analyzed in order to discover certain patterns of the triad components in design activity (shown in Fig. 2). In the graphical representations, the horizontal axis represents the order of a designer's thought processes, which correspond with the segment of a protocol. Due to a difference in total segment number, both the order of each designer's thought processes and the accumulative segments of each Triad category were normalized into 100.

In order to compare the increment per segment unit for each Triad category, we calculated the slope of the accumulative graph of each triadic category by estimating linear regressions. In simple linear regression the data model is written as $y_i = \beta_0 + \beta_1 x + \epsilon_i$, where ϵ_i is an observational error. β_0 (intercept) and β_1 (slope) are the parameters of the model (Linear Regression, 2011).

The results of our linear regressions are presented in Table 3. We had linear regressions that had the normalized order of each designer's thought processes as a predictor variable, and the normalized accumulative count of each triadic category as the criterion variable. The every linear regression model was significant, and the value of F , p , and adjusted R^2 of the model are described in the 3rd, 4th, and 5th columns in Table 3. The value of F and p explains the significance of regression, that is to say, if at least one of the regressors x_1, x_2, \dots, x_k contributes significantly to the model (Montgomery, 2001; Brace, Kemp, & Snelgar, 2000). The coefficient of

Figure 2. Accumulative segments of each Triad category of the designer number 1's problem-solving process of design task 1 (upper) and task 2 (lower)

determination R^2 is the proportion of variability in a data set that is accounted for by a statistical model, and the adjusted R^2 is a modification of R^2 that adjusts for the number of explanatory terms in a model (Montgomery & Peck, 1992; Coefficient of Determination, 2011).

In each regression, the coefficient of the normalized order variable was positive with a p -value less than 0.0005. The value of Beta and p of the predictor variable are shown in the 6th and 7th columns in Table 3. The standardized coefficient, Beta explains the contribution of each predictor variable to the model, and the p -value shows the influence of each predictor variable to the criterion variable (Montgomery & Peck, 1992; Brace, Kemp, & Snelgar, 2000).

When comparing the slope of each triadic category, all the samples except the designer number 1's task 2 displayed the slope of the S category most and that of the P category least. An ANOVA was conducted to examine the effects of the Triad categories on the slope. There was a significant effect of the Triad categories ($F_{(2, 14)} = 98.501, p < 0.0005$). The slope of S category ($M = .531$) was larger than the slope of G category ($M = .305; F_{(1, 15)} = 67.829, p < 0.0005$), and the slope of both of these categories were larger than the slope of P category ($M = .163; F_{(1, 15)} = 362.956, p < 0.0005$ for S category, and $F_{(1, 15)} = 29.296, p < 0.0005$ for G category). This indicates that as the problem-solving activities progressed, designers focus more on the S category while less on the P category.

CORRELATION BETWEEN PROTOCOL ANALYSIS RESULTS AND EVALUATION RESULTS

In order to examine how the triadic components are correlated with evaluation results, we estimated correlations among the patterns found from the protocol analysis and evaluation results.

The percentage of P category and the increment per segment unit for P category were significantly positively correlated with the designers' ratings on how much the designer redefined the design problem ($\rho = .595, N = 16, p < 0.05, 2$ -tailed, for the percentage of P category, and $\rho = .571, N = 16, p < 0.05, 2$ -tailed, for the increment per segment unit of P category): the more the number of P category and the increment of P category, the more does the designer redefine the design problem. The Spearman's rank correlation coefficient (ρ) is a non-parametric measure of correlation between two variables X and Y (Spearman's Rank Correlation Coefficient, 2011).

Designer	Task	Triad	The value of the model			The value of the predictor variable		Slope
			F	p	Adjusted R^2	Beta	p	
1	1	P	$F_{(1, 155)}=4168.086$.000	.964	.982	.000	.166
		G	$F_{(1, 155)}=33952.686$.000	.995	.998	.000	.336
		S	$F_{(1, 155)}=24964.249$.000	.994	.997	.000	.498
	2	P	$F_{(1, 190)}=6990.688$.000	.973	.987	.000	.254
		G	$F_{(1, 190)}=37745.966$.000	.995	.980	.000	.208
		S	$F_{(1, 190)}=37745.966$.000	.995	.997	.000	.538
2	1	P	$F_{(1, 152)}=1812.184$.000	.922	.961	.000	.217
		G	$F_{(1, 152)}=6309.150$.000	.977	.988	.000	.220
		S	$F_{(1, 152)}=9086.939$.000	.983	.992	.000	.563
	2	P	$F_{(1, 122)}=1898.703$.000	.939	.969	.000	.212
		G	$F_{(1, 122)}=8535.975$.000	.986	.993	.000	.288
		S	$F_{(1, 122)}=8535.975$.000	.986	.993	.000	.500
3	1	P	$F_{(1, 121)}=1072.800$.000	.898	.948	.000	.204
		G	$F_{(1, 121)}=6384.272$.000	.981	.991	.000	.215
		S	$F_{(1, 121)}=6736.726$.000	.982	.991	.000	.581
	2	P	$F_{(1, 150)}=3312.324$.000	.956	.978	.000	.147
		G	$F_{(1, 150)}=9522.003$.000	.984	.992	.000	.238
		S	$F_{(1, 150)}=43632.158$.000	.997	.998	.000	.615
4	1	P	$F_{(1, 93)}=546.383$.000	.853	.924	.000	.224
		G	$F_{(1, 93)}=2624.441$.000	.965	.983	.000	.269
		S	$F_{(1, 93)}=5864.056$.000	.967	.983	.000	.507
	2	P	$F_{(1, 117)}=983.171$.000	.893	.945	.000	.126
		G	$F_{(1, 117)}=4312.371$.000	.973	.987	.000	.337
		S	$F_{(1, 117)}=7359.003$.000	.984	.992	.000	.536
5	1	P	$F_{(1, 239)}=1415.023$.000	.855	.925	.000	.139
		G	$F_{(1, 239)}=51687.823$.000	.995	.998	.000	.412
		S	$F_{(1, 239)}=9752.006$.000	.976	.988	.000	.449
	2	P	$F_{(1, 156)}=2027.747$.000	.928	.964	.000	.069
		G	$F_{(1, 156)}=8065.290$.000	.981	.990	.000	.390
		S	$F_{(1, 156)}=11812.686$.000	.987	.993	.000	.541
6	1	P	$F_{(1, 146)}=842.422$.000	.851	.923	.000	.167
		G	$F_{(1, 146)}=7713.252$.000	.981	.991	.000	.389
		S	$F_{(1, 146)}=2403.570$.000	.942	.971	.000	.444
	2	P	$F_{(1, 96)}=2080.366$.000	.955	.978	.000	.115
		G	$F_{(1, 96)}=1826.155$.000	.950	.975	.000	.259
		S	$F_{(1, 96)}=7270.826$.000	.987	.993	.000	.626
7	1	P	$F_{(1, 225)}=8004.630$.000	.973	.986	.000	.183
		G	$F_{(1, 225)}=13251.359$.000	.983	.992	.000	.311
		S	$F_{(1, 225)}=63021.295$.000	.996	.998	.000	.505
	2	P	$F_{(1, 173)}=2448.338$.000	.934	.966	.000	.130
		G	$F_{(1, 173)}=22204.457$.000	.992	.996	.000	.380
		S	$F_{(1, 173)}=11882.585$.000	.986	.993	.000	.490
8	1	P	$F_{(1, 248)}=4685.842$.000	.950	.975	.000	.114
		G	$F_{(1, 248)}=16681.194$.000	.985	.993	.000	.304
		S	$F_{(1, 248)}=26498.469$.000	.991	.995	.000	.582
	2	P	$F_{(1, 168)}=10271.567$.000	.984	.992	.000	.146
		G	$F_{(1, 168)}=6162.603$.000	.973	.987	.000	.329
		S	$F_{(1, 168)}=22153.625$.000	.992	.996	.000	.525

Table 3. The slope of each Triad category

The percentage of G category was significantly positively correlated with the designers' ratings of the concept generation ($\rho = .522$, $N = 16$, $p < 0.05$, 2-tailed). This implies that the more do designers produce goals, the better do they generate the design concept. This result supports the positive effect of the goal-oriented problem-solving process of design on the concept generation.

The increment per segment unit for P category was significantly positively correlated with the functional utility ($\rho = .713$, $N = 16$, $p < 0.01$, 2-tailed). This indicates that as the increment of P category increases more, solutions with better functional utility are produced. That is to say, for better functional utility, more analysis of the problems is necessary.

DISCUSSION

Through protocol analysis, we identified general patterns of the triadic components: (i) The percentages of each triadic category were S (51.7%), G (32.0%), and P (16.3%). (ii) As the problem-solving activities progressed, designers focused more on the S category while less on the P category.

The patterns of the triadic components explain both-sided properties of design activity which simultaneously includes both the rational problem-solving paradigm and the paradigm of reflective practice. From a microscopic point of view, the triadic components were displayed by interacting each other, and this explains the reflective property of design activity. On the other hand, from a macroscopic point of view, designers' focus on the triadic components changed from P category to other categories, and from G category to S category, and this illustrates the rational search processes in rational problem solving paradigm.

In order to examine how the triadic components are associated with design task, process, and outcome, we estimated correlations among the patterns found from the protocol analysis and the designers' assessment results. We found several correlations between the triadic components and the evaluation results, including the positive correlation between

the percentage of P category and the designers' ratings on how much the designer redefined the design task, the positive correlation between the percentage of G category and the designers' ratings of the concept generation, and the positive correlation between the increment per segment unit for P category and the functional utility. These findings indicate how the dynamics of triadic components influenced design task, process, and outcome.

CONCLUSIONS

The objectives of this study were to investigate the general patterns of the triadic components drawn from the triad problem-solving model of design and to examine how the triadic components are associated with design task, process, and outcome.

To trace designers' design activity by triadic components, a protocol analysis was conducted with trashcan design task at two different determinization levels, and the data was coded with the Triad coding scheme which is composed of Problem (P), Goal (G), and Solution (S). The post-experiment survey was executed in order to evaluate the design problems, their process and solutions.

As a result, general patterns of the triadic components were identified including the different percentage and the increase rate of each triadic category. In problem-solving process of design, both the percentage and increase rate of the solution category were highest while those of the problem category were lowest. This indicates that designers spend most times on creating solutions while least times on analyzing design problems, and these patterns of the triadic components become more dominant as the problem-solving activities progressed. Through correlation analysis, we found that designers redefined the design task more when they identified more design problems. In addition, the correlation analysis results supported the positive effect of the goal-oriented problem-solving process on the concept generation as well as the

importance of the analyzing problems to produce solutions with better functional utility.

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